

A Quantum-Mechanical Particle in a Cornell-Type Potential in Lobachevsky Space

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In a Friedmann-Lobachevsky space-time with a radius of curvature slowly varying in time, we study numerically a problem of motion of a scalar particle moving in Cornell-type potentials. Considering both non-relativistic and relativistic cases and two possible generalizations of the Cornell potential we investigate the possibilities to find solutions with the definite energy decaying fast enough at infinity.

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1. Introduction

In the beginning of the quark hypothesis of particle structure, composite models based on non-relativistic problems for various potentials demonstrated their effectiveness. Within the framework of that approach, the mass spectra of a number of mesons and hadrons and some of their static characteristics were successfully described. Examples of the use of such models are given in reviews [1–3]. In approaches in which particles are considered as consisting of quarks, a special role belongs to the Cornell potential, which ensures confinement of quarks (see, for example, [4]). In Euclidean space Cornell potential has the form

$$V(r) = \frac{a}{r} + br. \quad (1)$$

Here we consider a generalization of this potential in the space of constant negative curvature, which we call Cornell-type potential. As far as we know, this problem has not yet been discussed in literature, although the idea to model interactions with the help of non-Euclidean geometry can be found in a number of papers [5, 6].

We study the effect of two Cornell-type potentials given by the equations

$$V(r) = \frac{a}{\rho} \coth(r\rho) + b\rho \sinh(r/\rho), \quad (2)$$

$$V(r) = \frac{a}{\rho} \coth(r\rho) + b\rho \tanh(r/\rho). \quad (3)$$

Both of these potentials become (1) when $r \rightarrow \infty$.

Note that the generalization of the Cornell potential is not unique. The first term in formulas (2) and (3) is the fundamental solution of the Laplace-Beltrami equation in three-dimensional Lobachevsky space. It corresponds to the Coulomb attraction. The choice of the

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second term is determined by taking into account different features of the initial Cornell potential (1). In (2) the second term corresponds to the linearly increasing potential in a flat space. The second term in (3) preserves the symmetry inherent in the flat limit of this potential. The first potential we will call “sinh-potential” and the second one – “tanh-potential”.

2. Non-relativistic scalar particle in Lobachevsky space

Let us consider the motion of a quantum particle in the Friedmann-Lobachevsky space-time [7–9] in assumption that the curvature radius $\rho(t)$ changes very slowly in time, and is considered as being constant, in particular, as it is in the Einstein’s solution [10]. Such an assumption is valid for a period of time δt satisfying the inequality $\rho'(t_0)\delta t \ll \rho(t_0)$ or $\delta t \ll H^{-1}$, where H is the Hubble constant [11].

We use the embedding of the Lobachevsky space into a 4-dimensional pseudo-Euclidean space, in which the Cartesian coordinates x_μ , $\mu = 1, 2, 3, 4$ are introduced, and for points in the Lobachevsky space the equality

$$\begin{aligned} x_\mu x_\mu &= \mathbf{x}^2 + x_4^2 = \mathbf{x}^2 - x_0^2 = -\rho^2, \\ \mathbf{x} &= (x_1, x_2, x_3), \quad x_4 = ix_0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

is valid.

The Schrödinger equation for the stationary states in the Lobachevsky space with a curvature radius ρ in spherical coordinates [12]

$$\begin{aligned} x_0 &= \rho \cosh \beta; & x_1 &= \rho \sinh \beta \sin \theta \cos \phi; \\ x_2 &= \rho \sinh \beta \sin \theta \sin \phi; & x_3 &= \rho \sinh \beta \cos \theta; \\ 0 &\leq \beta < \infty; & 0 &\leq \theta \leq \pi; & 0 &\leq \phi \leq 2\pi. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

has the form

$$-\frac{\hbar}{2m} \left(\frac{1}{\rho^2 \sinh^2 \beta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} \left(\sinh^2 \beta \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} \right) + \frac{1}{\rho^2 \sinh^2 \beta} \Delta_{\theta, \phi} \right) \psi + V \psi = E \psi, \quad (6)$$

where $\beta = r/\rho$.

In the case of a central symmetric potential $V = V(r)$, the equation (6) can be reduced to

$$-\frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2 u}{dr^2} + V_{eff}(r) u = \epsilon u, \quad (7)$$

where the effective potential reads

$$V_{eff}(r) = mV(r) + \frac{l(l+1)}{2\rho^2 \sinh^2(r/\rho)} + \frac{1}{2\rho^2}, \quad (8)$$

and $\epsilon = mE$. In this case, the wave function is written in terms of $u(r)$ and spherical harmonics as

$$\psi(r, \theta, \phi) = \frac{u(r)}{\sinh(r/\rho)} Y_{lm}(\theta, \phi). \quad (9)$$

Here, a rational system of units has been chosen, in which $c = \hbar = 1$ and all physical quantities have units of measurement of powers of the energy.

In the case of the potential (2) the effective potential has the form of an infinitely deep well, and therefore in this case the problem provides infinitely many bound states. The case (3) is more interesting.

Figures 1 and 2 show the plots of the effective interaction potential for different values of the curvature radius and orbital quantum number [12]. As we see the depth of the well in effective potential is a finite and it depends on the orbital quantum number l and the radius of curvature

FIG. 1: (Color online) Effective potential plot for different ρ .

FIG. 2: (Color online) Effective potential plot for different l .

ρ . As l increases (keeping ρ constant) the well becomes more and more shallow, and at some high enough value of l disappears: no bound states are possible. On the contrary, as we increase ρ and keep l unchanged, the well becomes deeper and we can have more bound states. In the limit when $\rho \rightarrow \infty$ we are back to the flat space with an infinite number of bound states. When ρ is small enough (which corresponds to the high curvature of the space, as it is supposed to take place in the early Universe) the well again disappears and we do not have bound states. As the curvature radius increases in time as in the Friedmann's solution for an open Universe model, a particle moving in the Cornell-type potential at first has no bound states, then it has higher and higher finite number

of bound states, and as ρ approaches infinity (space becomes flat), all states become bound.

Therefore, while in the flat space for the Cornell potential we have infinitely many bound states (all states are bound), in Lobachevsky space with the potential (3) there is a finite number of bound states. These states and corresponding energy levels we found numerically using the shooting method, at each step of which the differential equation (7) is numerically solved under initial conditions specified by the asymptotic expressions

$$\begin{aligned}
 u(r_0) &= [\tanh(r_0/\rho)]^{l+1}; \\
 u'(r_0) &= \frac{(l+1)[\tanh(r_0/\rho)]^l}{\rho \cosh^2(r_0/\rho)}, \quad (10)
 \end{aligned}$$

where a value of the variable r_0 is of order of 0.001.

The general steps of the numerical calculation are the following: we first decide upon the interval of r on which the numerical calculation will be performed and divide all the potential well into rather big energy intervals of order of 0.01. Solving the differential equation for each value of energy with the step of 0.01, we determine the approximate energy values for which the numerical solution to the differential equation calculated at the end of the interval changes sign when we go to the next energy value. Then we increase the accuracy of energy levels: we add one more digit to the approximate value (from 0 to 9) and find for which digit the solution changes sign. Proceeding to the next digits we obtain a wave function decaying at the end of the computational interval. The greater is the accuracy of the computation (the more extra digits we determine), the larger is the interval of convergence of the wave function. To be sure that there are no other bound states we consider the last energy interval and repeat the procedure for it with the step of the lower value. If we find a bound state in this energy interval we add it to our previously found states.

Let us denote

$$\epsilon_{max} = \lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} V_{eff}(r) = m \left(\frac{a}{\rho} + b\rho \right) + \frac{1}{2\rho^2}. \quad (11)$$

At the energies higher than ϵ_{max}/m , scattering occurs, while at lower energies bound states are possible.

For numerical computation we will assume the following values of parameters: $a = -0.5$ and $b = 0.18$, $m = 1$, $\rho = 10$.

Figures 3 and 4 show numerical solutions for bound states and their corresponding energy levels for $l = 1$. In this case, there are only 7 bound states.

Using the numerically calculated values of energy levels at different l , Regge trajectories were constructed (see Fig. 5). Here we use the same approach as in [13, 14]. It can be seen from the figure that as l increases the number of bound states decreases.

3. Relativistic scalar particle in Lobachevsky space

In this section we will consider the motion of a scalar relativistic particle in the field of the Cornell-type potential in Lobachevsky space. Note that in such problems the transition to quantum mechanics, as well as the generalization to the relativistic case, is not unambiguous. In order to write the Klein–Gordon–Fock equation, we proceeded from the following consideration.

The Hamiltonian of a relativistic particle of mass m , which moves in a field with potential $V(\vec{r})$, reads

$$H = m + K + V(\vec{r}), \quad (12)$$

where the first term is the rest energy, and the second one is the kinetic energy. From this equation it follows that

$$(H - V(\vec{r}))^2 = p^2 + m^2.$$

We will consider the case of the spherically symmetric potential, i. e. $V(\vec{r}) = V(r)$. Moving on to the operators $H = i\frac{\partial}{\partial t}$, $p^2 = -\Delta$ and acting on both parts of this equality on the function ϕ , we obtain the Klein-Gordon-Fock equation

$$\left(i\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - V(r) \right)^2 \phi = (-\Delta + m^2)\phi. \quad (13)$$

Since we are considering “states” with a certain energy, then $H\phi = E\phi$. Since the operators $\frac{\partial}{\partial t}$ and $V(r)$ commute, the last equation can be written as

$$(\Delta + (E - V(r))^2 - m^2)\phi = 0. \quad (14)$$

In the Lobachevsky space with a radius of curvature ρ

$$\Delta = \frac{1}{\rho^2 \sinh^2 \beta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} \left(\sinh^2 \beta \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} \right) + \frac{1}{\rho^2 \sinh^2 \beta} \Delta_{\theta, \phi}. \quad (15)$$

Separating the variables by

$$\phi = \frac{u(r)}{\sinh(r/\rho)} Y_{lm}(\theta, \varphi),$$

we obtain the equation for $u(r)$

FIG. 3: (Color online) First four numerical solutions for the bound states and corresponding energy levels.

FIG. 4: (Color online) Next three numerical solutions for the bound states and corresponding energy levels.

FIG. 5: (Color online) Regge trajectories.

$$\frac{d^2u(r)}{dr^2} + \left[(E - V(r))^2 - m^2 - \frac{1}{\rho^2} - \frac{l(l+1)}{\rho^2 \sinh^2(r/\rho)} \right] u(r) = 0.$$

Let us introduce two function V_1 and V_2 as $V_1 = V + Q, V_2 = V - Q,$

$$Q = \sqrt{m^2 + \frac{1}{\rho^2} + \frac{l(l+1)}{\rho^2 \sinh^2(r/\rho)}}.$$

Then, the last equation is transformed into

$$\frac{d^2u}{dr^2} + (E - V_1)(E - V_2)u(r) = 0. \quad (16)$$

We will search for numerical solutions to the equation (16) which tend to zero when $r \rightarrow \infty$. Such solutions can be found if the product $(E - V_1)(E - V_2)$ is negative at $r \rightarrow \infty$. First, we will consider the case of sinh-potential given by (2). Choosing the parameter values $\rho = 10$, $l = 1$, $m = 1$, we plot the functions $V_1(r)$ and $V_2(r)$ (see fig. 6).

We see that for any values of energy E , the product $(E - V_1)(E - V_2)$ is positive at infinity. Thus such solutions do not exist for this potential. Figures 7 and 8 show the actual numerical solutions for two arbitrarily selected values of energy.

FIG. 6: (Color online) $V_1(r)$ and $V_2(r)$ functions in the case of potential (2).

From the figures 7 and 8 we see that the solutions have oscillatory behaviour at infinity with decreasing amplitude.

Now let us plot the functions $V_1(r)$ and $V_2(r)$ for parameter values $m = 1$, $l = 1$, $\rho = 8$ in the case of tanh-potential (3). The graphs are represented on the figure 9.

In this case the solutions exponentially decreasing at infinity are possible for the values of energy of the range from $E_{min} = \lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} V_2(r)$ to $E_{max} = \lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} V_1(r)$. For the chosen values of parameters we find 5 such solutions which graphs

FIG. 7: A numerical solution in the case of potential (2) for $E = 1$.

FIG. 8: A numerical solution in the case of potential (2) for $E = 5$.

FIG. 9: (Color online) $V_1(r)$ and $V_2(r)$ functions in the case of potential (3).

FIG. 10: (Color online) Three numerical solutions for energies $E_n = 1.537197, 1.851153, 2.072669$.

FIG. 11: (Color online) Two numerical solutions for energies $E_n = 2.228895, 2.330277$.

FIG. 12: (Color online) Regge trajectories in the case of potential (3).

and corresponding energy values are shown on the figures 10 and 11.

The figure 12 shows the Regge trajectories for the calculated energy values.

4. Conclusion

In the paper we have investigated numerically the possibilities of exponentially decreasing solutions to non-relativistic and relativistic models of a quantum particle with a definite energy value in the Cornell-type

potential in Lobachevsky space. Two types of the generalizations of the Cornell potential have been discussed. In the non-relativistic case, sinh-potential provides an infinite number of the bound states, while for tanh-potential one find a finite number of such states. In the relativistic case, for the tanh-potential we again obtain a finite number of exponentially decaying solutions while for the sinh-potential there are no such solutions at all.

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